

Description of files

Periodic_Pressure: Variation of pressure for the periodic cases

Periodic_amp10Per100x09: Periodic, amplitude 10, period = 100, stress 90% of steady state

Periodic_amp15Per100x09: Periodic, amplitude 15, period = 100, stress 90% of steady state

Periodic_amp15Per200x09: Periodic, amplitude 15, period = 200, stress 90% of steady state

Periodic_amp10Per200x09: Periodic, amplitude 10, period = 200, stress 90% of steady state

Periodic_amp20Per200x08: Periodic, amplitude 20, period = 200, stress 80% of steady state

Periodic_amp20Per100x08: Periodic, amplitude 20, period = 100, stress 80% of steady state

Periodic_amp15Per200x08: Periodic, amplitude 15, period = 200, stress 80% of steady state

Periodic_amp15Per100x08: Periodic, amplitude 15, period = 100, stress 80% of steady state

Ramp9P20R120; Ramp, 90% of steady state, final pressure 2 MPa, ramp time 12 minutes

Ramp9P15R120; Ramp, 90% of steady state, final pressure 1.5 MPa, ramp time 12 minutes

Ramp9P10R120; Ramp, 90% of steady state, final pressure 1 MPa, ramp time 12 minutes

Ramp9P10R075; Ramp, 90% of steady state, final pressure 1 MPa, ramp time 7.5 minutes

Ramp9P10R060; Ramp, 90% of steady state, final pressure 1 MPa, ramp time 6 minutes

Ramp9P10R040; Ramp, 90% of steady state, final pressure 1 MPa, ramp time 4 minutes

ConPPRate9150a03: Constant pore pressure rate, 90 % steady state, 1.5 MPa/hr, alpha = 0.3

ConPPRate9100a03: Constant pore pressure rate, 90 % steady state, 1.0 MPa/hr, alpha = 0.3

Carbonate09ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_00: 90 % steady state, injection rate 1.0 MPa/hr, alpha =0.0

Carbonate09ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_00: 90 % steady state, injection rate 0.2 MPa/12 min, alpha =0.0

Carbonate08ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_00: 80 % steady state, injection rate 1.0 MPa/hr, alpha =0.0

Carbonate08ss_injection_rate_02_alpha_00: 80 % steady state, injection rate 0.2 MPa/12 min, alpha =0.0

Carbonate08ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_04: 80 % steady state, injection rate 1.0 MPa/hr, alpha =0.4

Carbonate09ss_injection_rate_02_alpha_04: 90 % steady state, injection rate 0.2 MPa/12 min, alpha =0.4

Carbonate09ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_04: 90 % steady state, injection rate 1 MPa/1 hr, alpha =0.4

Carbonate08ss_injection_rate_02_alpha_04: 80 % steady state, injection rate 0.2 MPa/12 min, alpha =0.4

Carbonate08ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_03: 80 % steady state, injection rate 1.0 MPa/hr, alpha =0.3

Loading Program

Carbonate09ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_03: 90 % steady state, injection rate 1.0 MPa/hr, alpha =0.3

Carbonate09ss_injection_rate_02_alpha_03: 90 % steady state, injection rate 0.2 MPa/12 min, alpha =0.3

Carbonate08ss_injection_rate_02_alpha_03: 80 % steady state, injection rate 0.2 MPa/12 min, alpha =0.3

Shale08ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_02: 80 % steady state, injection rate 1.0 MPa/hr, alpha =0.2

Shale08ss_injection_rate_02_alpha_02: 80 % steady state, injection rate 0.2 MPa/12 min, alpha =0.2

Shale09ss_injection_rate_02_alpha_02: 90 % steady state, injection rate 0.2 MPa/12 min, alpha =0.2

Shale09ss_injection_rate_10_alpha_02: 90 % steady state, injection rate 1.0 MPa/hr, alpha =0.2